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The transformation of industrial production in the regions is taking place under the influence of digitalization on the processes of technological sovereignty of the country in conditions of turbulent instability, which requires the development of digital infrastructure, the development of technologies at the regional level, ensuring their development. The regional development of industrial production will increase the competitiveness of the state, reduce barriers to business, and regions will become attractive to investors and innovative development by creating new production facilities, products, and goods. An analytical review of the theoretical approaches of Russian and foreign economists on this issue has been conducted, which allowed the author to identify theoretical, methodological and applied foundations for determining directions within the framework of the state strategy for planning the development of industrial production in the regions of Russia. The fundamental differences between the theoretical arguments of the proponents of digital technologies promoted and the really accelerated development of technological progress in the Russian industrial complex with a focus on platform development of the first and second generation are identified. A review of the theoretical approaches of various authors on the issues under study provides a broader range of tools for implementing the digital transformation of industrial production specifically in organizations, selecting their own matrix model of these transformational processes. Transformations are needed to preserve and strengthen the competitiveness of the state in the digital environment, and this area is a key trend in the industrial development of the territories. One of the decisive factors for the success of industrial production development is the use of digital technologies, taking into account the possibility of digital transformations in various development formats, which requires the formation of a theoretical and methodological integrated approach to developing a digital transformation strategy for regional industrial organizations based on the systematization of a successful strategic matrix structure of strategic archetypes. In this research vector, the author analyzes the features of the impact of various digital technologies on the ongoing processes in the transformation of industrial production, both the analysis of statistical data and the assessment of the degree of readiness of facilities for digitalization, as well as the available level of maturity of the relevant processes. An assessment of the digital maturity of industrial production organizations is given, which implies that supply chain integration, order management, forecasting, in the first place, is digitization, and horizontal integration with suppliers, customers, and other partners along the value chain, progress is slower than the vertical value chain. The study analyzes state support from the state budget with co-financing from regional budgets, and there are also tax incentives to ensure technological sovereignty. It is highlighted that most of the technologies are used in production processes, robotics, additive technologies, as well as a group of related technologies such as the Internet of Things; digital twins; digital design and modeling are leading here. Industrial organizations actively use digital technologies in the processes of new product development, sales, delivery and after-sales service, as well as in logistics. The analysis of regional development has been carried out and it has been revealed that many regions are developing in different ways, breakthrough regions are economically developed entities with digital transformation teams due to large-scale resources and concentration of IT technologies in business, lagging regions include those with a small budget, complex geography, outdated production facilities. The share of organizations using digital technologies has been determined: technologies for collecting, processing and analyzing big data and cloud services, which occupy the first place, Internet of Things technologies are in second place, artificial intelligence is in third place, industrial robots are in fourth, adaptive technologies are in fifth, digital twin is in sixth, and digital platforms. It is determined that the expanded matrix structure of strategic archetypes is built as an analytical structuring tool with an emphasis on comparability and internal consistency in the sequence of transformation of industrial production.

Keywords: public policy, regional economy, industrial production, industrial enterprises, key trends, flexibility of strategy, tools of the matrix structure of strategic archetypes.

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« »	140,58	121,0	201,14	215,14	220,0
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« »	1,32	1,32	1,43	1,43	1,44
« »	27,83	20,93	31,39	31,39	31,43
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	79,5	8,1	6,8	2,9	4,9	15,4	3,9
	71,1	47,0	3,9	5,8	2,5	3,9	1,9
	36,9	32,4	22,6	18,9	4,8	4,9	6,0
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	34,1	34,9	16,1	21,9	8,1	18,1	3,1
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•	.	21,8	25,0	25,6	28,9
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•	-	27,1	28,9	30,7	32,9
•	.	19,0	19,8	20,0	21,9
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•	-	15,8	17,6	15,6	16,9
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•	-	5,4	5,7	6,6	7,9
•	-	3,6	3,9	5,5	6,8
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•	-	5,2	5,7	5,6	6,1
•	.	1,5	0,9	1,0	1,4
•	-	1,1	1,4	1,3	1,6
•	-	3,3	3,8	3,5	3,9
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